

Deliverable 2.1

Open Healthcare Map v1

A selection of 45 best practices in 9 fields of application in Open Healthcare,
sourced from online repositories.

Date

December 2018

Dissemination Level

Public

Responsible Partners

Makea

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0 - Basic remarks about
requirements, tentative
methodology and continuing
research

0.1

REQUIREMENT

- WP 2 requires the deliverable of an **Open Healthcare Map** which includes **best practices of Open Healthcare solutions**. Best practices are very well executed examples openly documented individual solutions in Open Health & Wellbeing that deserve particular attention.
- In addition to selecting best practices, these cases shall be grouped in the most systematic way possible. For this purpose we use a **tentative taxonomy of nine application fields**, which will also structure the emerging careables.org.-platform if it proves to be consistent during our further applied research.
- Hence, it is necessary to first systematically sift through **all relevant repositories of Open Source solutions for Health & Wellbeing** and identify both the best practices and the most glaring gaps. Only on the basis of this map will it be possible to populate the careables.org platform with relevant solutions and to fill existing gaps in the Open Healthcare solutions landscape through the careables.org platform.

0.2

OVERALL APPROACH

- 1. Broadly scanning online repositories:** We scanned various online repositories for Open Health & Wellbeing to get an exact impression of the use cases that the different repositories are filled with (With deliverable 3.1, we have a separate deliverable in the project that focuses on a systematic review of all relevant online repositories.) It was noticed that "the usual suspects" - Instructables and Thingiverse - actually contain many of the best solutions, albeit in an extremely heterogeneous representation.
- 2. Casting best practices:** We then selected particularly convincing projects from the scanned pool of use cases. We tried to identify five projects per category in order to cover the entire range of applications, including niche applications.
- 3. Summarizing learnings:** Finally, the best practices group underwent a loose evaluation in which we reflected on the consequences that could be derived for the population of the Careables platform. This included, for example, the important question in which application areas we should make special efforts within the framework of the project to fill gaps. Another important question concerns the linking vs. reproduction of existing solutions: should we re-document the published solutions in a streamlined way or just link them?

0.3

OUR 'TAXONOMY'

<p>Therapy</p>		
<p>Careware</p>		
<p>Fun & Leisure Time</p>		

0.4

3 INTERSECTION SETS

0.5

HOW TO EVALUATE?

- Various methods can be used to identify best practices. As the project group cannot and will not present a final system at present, only the following four parameters will be listed here, which substantially guide our **qualitative and preliminary classification**:
 1. degree of precision and user-friendliness,
 2. technical reproducibility respectively feasibility,
 3. financial reproducibility
 4. editability for optimization by other users of the use case.
- In order to select the documented use cases, the working group has drawn on **three sources**:
 1. independent makers/makerspaces practitioners and managers
 2. users of the documented projects
 3. external experts in Open Healthcare research, drawn from the Advisory Board of project Careables

0.6

CONTINUING RESEARCH

There is a certain amount of academic and non-academic research on the availability of Open Healthcare solutions that our research group can draw on respectively to which our research group can refer to whoever is interested in continuing research. To name just three valuable publications:

1. With regard to the **user behaviour on the online repositories as such** we have looked at, the research group of this project will not address this issue through social network analysis and NLP-based methodology, although this is methodologically plausible. However, we would like to refer you to a detailed study by Homan, Schull, Prabhu (2017).
2. With regard to assistive projects on Thingiverse, Buehler et al. (2015) have published an excellent paper in which the authors conclude that **a closer exchange between developers and users seems useful**, which is a declared goal of careables.org.
3. This presentation by Amy Hurst focuses more on **therapeutical implications of 3D printing technology**.

1 - Overview of Open Healthcare repositories from which we sourced best practices*

*The selection is a less extensively commented version of the selection from Deliverable 3.1

1.1

ROUGH OVERVIEW

Title	Language	Website ranking	Nr of projects	Complexity	Specificity
Instructables www.instructable.com	English	910	$20 < x < 100$	Medium (format: BOM; steps). Not clear if the explanations are complete (technical drawings are often missing)	various categories
OpenThings www.openthings.wiki	English/ Dutch	not available	< 20	"Easy"	various categories
Thingiverse www.thingiverse.com	English	1290	> 100	"Easy"	various categories

1.2

ROUGH OVERVIEW

Title	Language	Website ranking	Nr of projects	Complexity	Specificity
Github github.com	English	70	> 100	For advanced users only.	various categories
Wevolver www.wevolver.com	English	725.733	> 100	For advanced users only.	various categories
Hackaday www.hackaday.io	English	21.646	> 100	"Easy"	various categories

1.3

ROUGH OVERVIEW

Title	Language	Website ranking	Nr of projects	Complexity	Specificity
Hackster www.hackster.io	English	16,446	> 100	Medium. Not clear if all the instructions are provided	various categories
Duino4projects duino4projects.com	English	283.656	$20 < x < 100$	Medium. Not clear if the explanations are complete or clear	various categories
Arduino Project Hub create.arduino.cc/projecthub	English	2.390	> 100	"Easy"	various categories

1.4

ROUGH OVERVIEW

Title	Language	Website ranking	Nr of projects	Complexity	Specificity
My Mini Factory www.myminifactory.com/	various languages	18,269	$20 < x < 100$	"easy"	various categories
wikifab wikifab.org/wiki/Accueil	various languages	431,446	$20 < x < 100$	"easy"	various categories
Youmagine www.youmagine.com	English	80.666	$20 < x < 100$	Not clear if the explanations are complete - no steps	various categories

1.5

ROUGH OVERVIEW

Title	Language	Website ranking	Nr of projects	Complexity	Specificity
Makers making change www.makersmakingchange.com	English	2.370.031	< 20	"Easy"	only health
Yeggi www.yeggi.com	English	17,196	> 100	"Easy"	various categories
Fabble fabble.cc	English/ Japanese	1,435,382	< 20	In Japanese	various categories

1.6

ROUGH OVERVIEW

Title	Language	Website ranking	Nr of projects	Complexity	Specificity
HTH www.hthumanitarians.org/page/toolbox	English	not available	$20 < x < 100$	"easy". The instructions are hosted in other platforms like Github	various categories
Eddy eddiy.es/doku.php?id=soluciones_segun_diagnostico:soluciones	Spanish	11,375,867	$20 < x < 100$	There's a video explaining the solution but not detailed instructions.	only health
Eddy Peru www.eddiy.pe/doku.php?id=vida_independiente:conjunto_de_soluciones_publicadas	Spanish	not available	$20 < x < 100$		only health

1.7

ROUGH OVERVIEW

Title	Language	Website ranking	Nr of projects	Complexity	Specificity
Appropedia www.appropedia.org	English	225260	$20 < x < 100$	Not only project but also information on specific topic. When documentation is provided, a description is given, step-by-step guide seem not detailed, link to external platform for further details.	various categories
Meviro www.meviro.org	Brazilian/ English	not available	$20 < x < 100$	The instructions seem easy and clear: materials needed, steps of construction, images	only health

2 - 45 best practices in Open
Healthcare grouped in 9 application
categories

2.1.1

LEARNING SUPPORT

Subject 2:
Communication in learning
disability care and support

Learning Disabilities Core Skills Education and Training Framework

This Framework was commissioned and funded by the Department of Health and developed in collaboration by Skills for Health, Skills for Care and Health Education England.

Introduction

People (children, young people and adults) with learning disabilities face particular challenges around communication. A learning disability affects the way a person understands information and how they communicate and most people (children, young people and adults) with learning disabilities have some difficulties with speech, language, communication and/or sensory impairment. These can be hidden or overlooked. It is therefore important to know what good communication support 'looks like', how organisations can contribute to minimising communication difficulties and what reasonable adjustments may be needed.

In order to communicate effectively it is essential to understand and value an individual's speech, language, sensory and communication needs and preferences.

Target audience

Tier 2 staff that will have some regular contact with people (children, young people and adults) with a learning disability

Tier 3 staff providing care and support for people (children, young people and adults) with a learning disability

<http://www.skillsforhealth.org.uk/images/resource-section/projects/learning-disabilities/Learning-Disabilities-CSTF.pdf>

2.1.2

LEARNING SUPPORT

Helping Children with Learning Disabilities

Practical Parenting Tips for Home and School

Has your child recently been diagnosed with a learning disability? Did you immediately begin to worry about how he or she will cope with school? It's only natural to want the best for your child but academic success, while important, isn't the end goal. What you really want for your child is a happy and fulfilling life. With encouragement and the right support,

Is your child a visual learner?

If your child is a visual learner, he or she:

- ▶ Learns best by seeing or reading
- ▶ Does well when material is presented and tested visually, not verbally
- ▶ Benefits from written notes, directions, diagrams, charts, maps, and pictures
- ▶ May love to draw, read, and write; is probably a good speller

Is your child an auditory learner?

If your child is an auditory learner, he or she:

- ▶ Learns best by listening
- ▶ Does well in lecture-based learning environments and on oral reports and tests
- ▶ Benefits from classroom discussions, spoken directions, study groups
- ▶ May love music, languages, and being on stage

Is your child a kinesthetic learner?

If your child is a kinesthetic learner, he or she:

- ▶ Learns best by doing and moving
- ▶ Does well when he or she can move, touch, explore, and create in order to learn
- ▶ Benefits from hands-on activities, lab classes, props, skits, and field trips

<https://www.helpguide.org/articles/autism-learning-disabilities/helping-children-with-learning-disabilities.htm?pdf=true>

2.1.3

LEARNING SUPPORT

The screenshot shows the LD@school website. At the top left is the logo 'LD@school' with a speech bubble icon. To the right is a 'Conn' button and a 'TA@l'école' button. Below the logo is a navigation bar with links: 'About Us', 'Learn About LDs', 'Resources', 'Learning Modules', and 'Educators' Institute'. The main content area has a dark teal background with the title 'Assistive Technology for Students with Learning Disabilities' in white. Below the title is a 'Previous' button. At the bottom, there is a 'Print Resource' button.

<https://www.ldatschool.ca/assistive-technology/>

About Us	Learn About LDs	Resources	Learning Modules	Educators' Institute
			meanings and associations with other words and concepts.	
Speaking	Cue cards – Cue cards provide helpful hints for the oral presentation of information, and the process of composing cue cards can help organize the information before-hand.	Prezi – A free 3D graphic organizer which can be used to create presentations. Prezis can be collaborative as students can comment and build upon other Prezis.	ShowMe Interactive Whiteboard –In order to reduce anxiety, students may opt to record presentations on their iPad beforehand. Video recordings can be uploaded on YouTube or a more private domain.	
		Kurzweil 3000 – Text-to-		

2.1.4

LEARNING SUPPORT

DISCOVER START PROJECT SEARCH

Auckland University of Technology

KiliRo

Biomimetics Healthcare

Overview
Images

Overview

MDPI Journals A-Z Information & Guidelines Initiatives About Login Register

robotics

Title / Keyword: Journal: Robotics
Author / Affiliation: Article Type: all

Advanced Search

Volume 6, Issue 1

Article Versions

- Abstract
- Full-Text PDF (1068 KB)
- Full-Text HTML
- Full-Text XML
- Full-Text Epub
- Article Versions Notes

Related Info

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- on DOAJ
- on Google Scholar
- on PubMed

Export Article

- BibTeX
- EndNote
- RIS

Robotics 2017, 6(1), 4; doi:10.3390/robotics6010004

Open Access

Article

Robot-Assisted Therapy for Learning and Social Interaction of Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder

Jaishankar Bharatharaj *

Institute of Biomedical Technologies, Auckland University of Technology, Auckland 1142, New Zealand

<https://www.wevolver.com/wevolver.staff/kiliro/master/blob/Overview.md>

2.1.5

LEARNING SUPPORT

Step 3: Drilling the Attachment Holes

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Reading-Aid/>

2.1.6

LEARNING SUPPORT

OpenBraille, a DIY Braille Embosser

By ccampos7 in Technology > Assistive-technology 14,066 135 15 Featured

<https://www.instructables.com/id/OpenBraille-a-DIY-Braille-Embosser/>

2.1.7

OUR LEARNINGS

- The Learning Support field is equally important for users and their families and challenging from the mapping perspective. For users and their relatives, such as parents of mentally handicapped children, good learning supports offer a way to gain sovereignty. Cognitive skills and knowledge are valuable resources, especially for people with disabilities, because they can make a significant contribution to gaining deeper access to society, for example in the form of jobs or simply through the ability to participate in conversations at eye level with fellow human beings.
- From a mapping perspective it can be stated that a general distinction between two dimensions: (1) process knowledge, e.g. instructions for dealing with challenging framework conditions of learners, on the one hand, and (2) (connected) hardware that support learning on the other hand, seems to make sense.
- As far as our platform content in these two dimensions is concerned, we would like to distinguish between five basic categories that are relevant from a user perspective: (1) hearing, (2) seeing, (3) reading, (4) writing and (5) other knowledge; the latter could include, for example, the acquisition of very specific forms of knowledge.

2.2.1

COMMUNICATION

Step 1: Understand the Block Diagram

10R81R1 C/F70WNP7H0R81R1 C1 ARGF.indd

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Intro-High-Frequency-Hearing-Loss-and-the-Frequnc/>

2.2.2

COMMUNICATION

Ok, next you need to solder the wires back to the speakers.

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Hearing-Protection-Headphone-Conversion-for-iPod/>

2.2.3

COMMUNICATION

	Quantity	Cost	Total	
	2	5	\$3.90	\$19.50
	0	1	\$3.67	\$3.67
	10-2	4	\$2.79	\$11.16
s Resistors	39	\$0.01	\$0.39	
s Capacitors	20	\$0.10	\$2.00	
Ah Battery	1	\$7.95	\$7.95	
o Mega onents	1	\$16.00	\$16.00	

The circuit for the hearing aid must accomplish several key tasks. First it has to amplify the microphone signal to a large enough level to be processed by the rest of the circuit. Next the signal has to be passed through a set of filters to split up the signal into four audio bands to be level estimated and then individually scaled. Finally the bands must be

cdn.instructables.com/FZL/MYGX/HOUFWVRZ/FZL/MYGX/HOUFWVRZ/LARGE.jpg and sent to a pair of headphones. The Arduino reads the levels of each band

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Intelligent-Hearing-Aid/>

2.2.4

COMMUNICATION

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Assistive-Phone-Case-for-Limited-Dexterity/>
gravityisweak [Follow](#)

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Assistive-Phone-Case-for-Limited-Dexterity/>

2.2.5

COMMUNICATION

The screenshot shows the Instructables website interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with the Instructables logo, a search bar, and links for 'Featured', 'Write an Instructable', 'Login', and 'Sign Up'. Below this, there are tabs for 'Classes', 'Contests', 'Community', and 'Teachers'. The main content area features the title 'Hand Gesture to Language Converter' by user 'Akashbabu39' in the 'Technology > Electronics' category. It has 2,588 views, 39 likes, and 2 comments. The post is marked as 'Featured'. Below the text, there are two images: the left one shows a laptop, a breadboard with electronic components, and a glove; the right one is a close-up of the glove with a sensor and wires attached to the back of the hand. At the bottom left of the image area, there is a small text overlay: 'Warten auf cd.instructables.com...'.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with multiple tabs open. The active tab displays the URL 'https://www.instructables.com/id/Hand-Gesture-to-Language-Converter/'. Below the address bar, there are navigation icons for 'Add Tip', 'Ask Question', 'Comment', and 'Download'.

Step 1: Preparing Your Edison Board

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Hand-Gesture-to-Language-Converter/>

2.2.6

OUR LEARNINGS

- From a mapping perspective it can be stated that a distinction between process knowledge, e.g. instructions for dealing with challenging framework conditions of learners, on the one hand, and physical tools that support learning on the other hand, seems to make sense. Obviously, there are large overlaps here. Nevertheless, the distinction seems to us to make sense, because while the first field is about ACQUIRING the basic skills and other forms of knowledge, the field "Communication" is about concrete IMPROVEMENT of the possibilities to communicate with other people.
- From the perspective of the Careables platform, it is interesting to see which different communication fields should be narrowed down. While the [WHO uses a very differentiated system for classifying, of functioning, disability and health](#), this would probably be overly differentiated for the Careables platform: WHO distinguishes between receiving verbal and non-verbal messages and producing them. This results in at least four sub-fields. We only want to create two sub-categories: (1) Communicating based on spoken messages and (2) Communicating based on non-verbal messages. Through this we do not differentiate between originators and recipients of messages.

2.3.1

MOBILITY

Tact: Low-cost, Advanced Prosthetic Hand
By Patrick S in Technology > 3D-Printing 👁️ 31,151 ❤️ 412 💬 16 🌟 Featured

[Download](#) [Favorite](#)

<https://cdn.instructables.com/FX7CXAM/916WA6RH/FX7OXAM/916WA6RH1ARGF.ino>

Step 1: Performance Comparison

Nominal Voltage (V)	Stall Current (A)	Watts (J)	Mc Tor
2	0.3	3.6	0.1
5	0.919	4.135	0.1

Finger	Avg. Speed (°/s)	Avg. Force (N)
Tact	289.8	4.21
Dextrus	175.4	1.71
i-LIMB Large (middle)	81.8	7.66
i-LIMB Med (index/ring)	95.3	5.39
i-LIMB Small (title)	95.4	5.17
i-LIMB Pulse Med (index)	60.5	4.15
i-LIMB Pulse Large (middle)	60.5	3.09
i-LIMB Pulse Med (ring)	74.3	6.43
i-LIMB Pulse Small (title)	82.2	4.09
Behionic (index)	45.8	12.47
Behionic (middle)	45.8	12.25
Behionic (ring)	45.8	12.53
Behionic Small (title)	37.8	16.11
Behionic v2 Large (ring, middle, and index)	96.4	14.5
Vincet Large (ring, middle, and index)	103.3	4.82
Vincet Small (title)	2	3.00

ipQ [2 More Images](#)

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Tact-Low-cost-Advanced-Prosthetic-Hand/>

2.3.2

MOBILITY

<https://www.anderes-sehen.de/akustische-orientierung-mobilitat/bauanleitung-fur-kinderlangstock/>

2.3.3

MOBILITY

2.3.4

MOBILITY

The screenshot shows the Instructables website interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Let's Make ..." and a search icon. To the right of the search bar are buttons for "Featured" and "Write an Instructable". Below the search bar, there are navigation links for "Classes", "Contests", "Community", and "Teachers". The main content area features the project title "Open Lights MADE FOR MY WHEELCHAIR" by user "weibeable" in the "Technology" category. The project has 9,933 views, 86 likes, and 26 comments. Below the text, there are two images: on the left, a woman in a wheelchair with glowing lights on the wheels at night, with the text "MADE FOR MY WHEELCHAIR" and a wheelchair icon; on the right, a close-up of a hand touching a glowing rectangular light strip next to a circular ring of red LEDs.

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Open-Lights-MADE-FOR-MY-WHEELCHAIR/>

This screenshot shows the "Step 1: Preparation - Materials, Tools & Technologies" section of the project page. It features two images: the left image shows a workbench with a green mat, a red multimeter, various tools like pliers and a screwdriver, and electronic components; the right image shows a blue and white "zing" 3D printer. Below these images, there is a grid of smaller images showing the assembly process, including a close-up of the LED ring and hands working on the circuit board.

2.3.5

MOBILITY

The screenshot shows the Thingiverse website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Thingiverse' logo, 'DASHBOARD', 'EXPLORE', 'EDUCATION', and 'CREATE'. A search bar and 'SIGN IN / JOIN' link are also present. The main content area features the project title 'The Raptor Hand by e-NABLE' by user 'e-NABLE', dated 'Sep 29, 2014'. Below the title is a large image of the 3D printed hand. To the right of the image is a 'DOWNLOAD ALL FILES' button and a statistics table:

Like	768
Collect	836
Comments	52
Post a Make	39
Watch	43
Remix It	10

At the bottom of the page, there is a cookie consent banner with an 'I AGREE' button.

This screenshot shows a 3D model of the Raptor Hand in a yellow color. Red arrows point to specific features with text annotations: 'Elastics now tie off here' and 'Non-flexible cords feed through here'. To the right of the model is a sidebar with a 'DOWNLOAD ALL FILES' button and a statistics table:

Like	768
Collect	836
Comments	52
Post a Make	39
Watch	43
Remix It	10
Share	0

Below the model is a cookie consent banner with an 'I AGREE' button.

<https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:476403>

2.3.6

MOBILITY

HACKADAY.IO Projects Lists Contests Stack More Search projects, profiles ... Sign up Log In

Affordable Exoskeleton Arm (ExoArm)

An affordable Exoskeleton Arm (ExoArm), that will help elderly, disabled people and workers complete everyday tasks with less exhaustion.

Krisijan Berce

Follow project Like project

Join this project

38.6k views 33 comments 307 followers 253 likes

Description Details Files 1 Components 15 Logs 11 Instructions 0 Discussion 33

DESCRIPTION
I remember watching my grandmother struggling when moving heavy things around when I was younger. So when I was 15, I had big plans on making an exoskeleton arm that would help her. I

38.6k views 33 comments 307 followers 253 likes

2017

Join this project

Affordable Exoskeleton Arm

<https://hackaday.io/project/20663-affordable-exoskeleton-arm-exoarm>

2.3.7

OUR LEARNINGS

- There is no doubt that mobility is one of the most important (open) health categories; in any case, it is the category from which the most impressive and popular use cases originate. Prosthetics projects based on Open Source are considered by many to be representative of all efforts to gather Open Source knowledge for Health & Wellbeing online and offline. This is no coincidence: fighting for physical freedom of movement is one of the greatest wishes that many physically handicapped people have. A cursory examination of use cases from online repositories shows that, as is to be expected, there is an enormous gap between easily replicable mobility aids and highly complex solutions; the latter often cannot be used reliably in the long term, as our qualitative interviews have shown. *There seems to be an extreme difference between the public perception of the relevance of such complex solutions and the actual benefit for users.*
- While existing online platforms do not differentiate further within the field of "mobility", the Careables platform should differentiate here in order to guide users of the platform more quickly to suitable solutions. The WHO essentially differentiates between six fields: (1) Lifting and carrying objects, (2) Fine hand use (picking up, grasping), (3) Walking, (4) Moving around using equipment (wheelchair, skates, etc.), (5) Using transportation (car, bus, train, plane), (6) Driving (riding bicycle & motorbike, driving). In order to reduce complexity, we make a distinction on the Careables platform between the following categories: (1) Upper body prosthetics & orthotics, (2) Lower body prosthetics & orthotics, (3) Moving around using individual mobility vehicles, (4) Moving around using public mobility vehicles.

2.4.1

INDOOR INSTALLATIONS

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Doorbell-that-Turns-on-a-Light/>

2.4.2

INDOOR INSTALLATIONS

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

The **gantries** were built out of softwood (fir) beams of 38 mm X 63 mm (1.5 in X 2.5 in) and 2.4 m in length. For the transversal beams, sections with a little notch

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Disabled-hoist-lift/>

2.4.3

INDOOR INSTALLATIONS

The screenshot shows a web interface for a project titled "Oven Door Opener". On the left is a dark sidebar with navigation options: "SIGN UP", "LOGIN", "CONNECT", "PROJECTS", and "EVENTS". The main content area displays the project title and a brief description: "Simple hack to open oven door." Below this, there are four metadata fields: "STAGE" (Prototype), "PROJECT NEED" (Agility / Dexterity, Mobility), "CREATED BY" (Makers Making Change), and "CAPABILITIES NEEDED" (Other). At the bottom, the "CREATIVE COMMONS LICENSE" is listed as "attribution-sharealike-4-0-international". A video thumbnail on the right shows a woman using the device to open an oven door.

SIGN UP

LOGIN

CONNECT

PROJECTS

EVENTS

Oven Door Opener

Simple hack to open oven door.

STAGE
Prototype

PROJECT NEED
Agility / Dexterity, Mobility

CREATED BY
Makers Making Change

CAPABILITIES NEEDED
Other

CREATIVE COMMONS LICENSE
attribution-sharealike-4-0-
international

STAGE

Prototype

PROJECT NEED

Agility / Dexterity, Mobility

CREATED BY

Makers Making Change

CAPABILITIES NEEDED

Other

CREATIVE COMMONS LICENSE

attribution-sharealike-4-0-
international

To make it easier for someone with low dexterity to open the door of an oven, a key ring is attached with a cable tie to the oven door handle.

<https://www.makersmakingchange.com/project/oven-door-opener/>

2.4.4

INDOOR INSTALLATIONS

https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:1055109

by Recidal Oct 6, 2015

RECIDAL DESIGN

DREAMER

CT

DOWNLOAD ALL FILES

- Like 120
- Collect 145
- Comments 2
- Post a Make 0
- Watch 5
- Remix It 1
- Share 0

Thing Apps Enabled

- Order This Printed
- View All Apps

https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:1055109

RECIDAL DESIGN

TESTING PARTS

RECIDAL DESIGN

DOWNLOAD ALL FILES

- Like 120
- Collect 145
- Comments 2
- Post a Make 0
- Watch 5
- Remix It 1
- Share 0

Thing Apps Enabled

- Order This Printed
- View All Apps

<https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:105510>

2.4.5

INDOOR INSTALLATIONS

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:1740932>. The page title is "Toilet Paper Holder for Disabled Access Hand Rail" by GavinLeigh, dated Aug 28, 2016. The main image shows a roll of white toilet paper mounted on a silver handrail using a black plastic holder. To the right of the image is a list of actions and their counts:

Like	18
Collect	19
Comments	0
Post a Make	0
Watch	0
Remix It	0
Share	0

Below the list, it says "Thing Apps Enabled".

This image is a close-up view of the toilet paper holder installed on a silver handrail. The holder is a black plastic device that fits around the handrail and holds a roll of toilet paper. The image is part of a gallery, with navigation arrows visible on the left and right sides. Below the main image is a row of five smaller thumbnail images showing different views of the holder.

<https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:1740932>

2.4.6

OUR LEARNINGS

- As far as our project group is aware, there is no online repository that uses indoor or outdoor installations as a separate category, either implicitly or explicitly. This is unfortunate, because solutions of this kind - fixed installations in the home or public spatial environment of people - complement body guided solutions perfectly.
- By "indoor installations" we mean more or less fixed physical solutions that make life easier for people with health-well-being impairments. As a rule, they find their place in the user's living area and are therefore tailored to individual spatial requirements.
- A particularly good, but also complicated example is the Disabled Hoist Lift, which can also be used in stairwells where commercial solutions cannot be used. Small solutions or hacks, however, which often overlap with the "Self Care" area, are much simpler. For example, it can be very helpful for users to be able to attach a fold-out holder for their usual coffee cup to their favourite desk.

2.5.1

OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Portable-Wheelchair-ramps/>

2.5.2

OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Hanging-planters/>

By **J_Boi** [Follow](#)

More by the author:

The goal is to make a planter which is applicable for all wheelchair users and to provide a better ergonomic height for personal suitability, even without wheelchair.

INTENSIVE PROGRAM HANGING PLANTER [Später ansehen](#) [Teilen](#)

[instructables.com/FR6M312/H1PABZ/FR6M312/H1PABZ/LARGE.jpg](https://www.instructables.com/FR6M312/H1PABZ/FR6M312/H1PABZ/LARGE.jpg)

2.5.3

OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS

The screenshot shows the Thingiverse interface for a project titled "3D printed Wheelchair-Ramp for one step" by user "nanonan", dated Dec 26, 2013. The main image shows a person in a wheelchair using a yellow ramp to cross a single step on a sidewalk. To the right of the image is a list of statistics and actions:

- Like: 911
- Collect: 386
- Comments: 65
- Post a Make: 1
- Watch: 18
- Remix It: 2
- Share: 0

At the bottom of the statistics list, it says "Thing Apps Enabled".

<https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:213181>

2.5.4

OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS

DIY Raised Bed Planter

By rhydlife in Workshop > Woodworking Featured

11 People Made This Project!

randy22977 made it!

EduardB20 made it!

RyanM07 made it!

MatthewM150 made it!

keall made it!

JohnSawtelle made it!

<https://www.instructables.com/id/DIY-Raised-Bed-Planter/>

2.5.5

OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS

Wheelchair Accessible Picnic Table

Jun 7, 2016 | Jamison Rantz | 3 Comments

Cut List

2 x 8 x 8' (Qty 5)

2 x 6 x 8' (Qty 4)

2 x 6 x 12'

2 x 4 x 8' (Qty 2)

<https://roqueengineer.com/diy-wheelchair-accessible-picnic-table-plans/>

2.5.6

OUR LEARNINGS

- According to our research, outdoor installations for people with health-well-being impairments are strongly underrepresented in online repositories. There may be obvious reasons for this: in purely legal terms, the fixed establishment of physical solutions in favour of people with health and well-being impairments is often not trivial - interventions in public spaces are subject to high regulatory hurdles. However, this is exactly what is exciting, because in places such as playgrounds, but also on private properties, the lives of people with disabilities take place. The use cases to be collected on the Carebles platform should therefore aim on the one hand to help those responsible for the outdoor design of private living areas and on the other hand to encourage those responsible for the design of public spaces to make them more inclusive.

2.6.1

SELF CARE

<https://www.thingiverse.com/thing/809953>

Thingiverse DASHBOARD EXPLORE EDUCATION CREATE Search Thingiverse SIGN IN / JOIN

Hey! This thing is still a Work in Progress. Files, instructions, and other stuff might change!

 Handled! Assistive Kitchen: T-Handle mold
by [zklogan](#) May 27, 2015

[DOWNLOAD ALL FILES](#)

Like	61
Collect	75
Comments	2
Post a Make	0
Watch	0
Remix It	0
Share	0

<https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:809953>

2.6.2

SELF CARE

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Assistive-Dining-Device-Arm-Sling/>

2.6.3

SELF CARE

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Custom-Assistive-Spoon/>

2.6.4

SELF CARE

PowerPoint Presentation - Adobe Acrobat Reader DC
Datei Bearbeiten Anzeige Fenster Hilfe

Start Werkzeuge PowerPoint Present... x

12 / 66 99%

Field Ready

Pipe Clamp	Readiness Levels				Risk
	Field 5	Maker 5	User 5	Tech 5	5

Name: Pipe Clamp
Part Number: WA001

Purpose: This is a collar used to attach a hose to the primary water output of a diesel water pump. It is suitable for a pipe that is approximately 3" OD.

Material: ABS Plastic

Additional Items Needed: None

Usage Notes: It requires sealing to be watertight.

Download file here: <http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:2464319>

PowerPoint Presentation - Adobe Acrobat Reader DC
Datei Bearbeiten Anzeige Fenster Hilfe

Start Werkzeuge PowerPoint Present... x

12 / 66 99%

Water Cap	Readiness Levels				Risk
	Field 5	Maker 5	User 5	Tech 5	5

Name: Pipe Clamp
Part Number: WA002

Purpose: This is a prototype threaded cap to seal off the excess water output of a diesel water pump. The thread is 1.66mm pitch (~1.5TP), about 1" OD. This is close to 3/4BSP but slightly smaller and finer pitch.

Material: ABS Plastic

Additional Items Needed: None

Download file here: <http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:2464301>

2.6.5

SELF CARE

The screenshot shows the Instructables website interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Let's Make ..." and a search icon. To the right of the search bar are links for "Featured" and "Write an Instructable". Further right are "Login" and "Sign Up" links. Below the search bar, there are navigation links for "Classes", "Contests", "Community", and "Teachers". On the right side, there is an "AUTODESK. Make anything" logo. The main content area features the title "Wearable Assistive Tech Gripper: Doraemon's Hand" in bold. Below the title, it says "By SP DASE 1996 in Technology > Assistive-technology" followed by statistics: "17,819" views, "162" likes, "9" comments, and a "Featured" star icon. There are also "Download" and "Favorite" icons. Below the text, there are two images: the left one shows a close-up of a black and red gripper holding a green highlighter, and the right one shows a person wearing the gripper on their hand, reaching for a red object on a table.

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Wearable-Assistive-Tech-Gripper-Doraemons-Hand/>

2.6.6

OUR LEARNINGS

- The sixth field of application - Self Care - is one of the most populated fields yet. It includes solutions that make it easier for people to take care of their physical hygiene and nutrition in view of their limitations. Not infrequently, solutions documented here could also be understood as indoor installations. Typical, however, are the small tools that are used every day, such as brushes and other washing utensils or cooking utensils, which are easy to grasp if you can't cope with conventionally proportioned utensils.
- From the point of view of the Careables platform, this field is also important because it contains many solutions that can be reproduced even by laypersons.
- We also assume that self-care solutions are particularly well suited to develop synergies with the Match-my-Maker project. The aim of this project is to bring people with careable needs together with technically savvy makers and thus support the "day-to-day business" of developing careables. Self-care-careables could well be produced in such a co-creation, because they are usually not technically highly complex and only work if the user is addressed in detail.

2.7.1

THERAPY

The screenshot shows the Instructables website interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Let's Make ..." and a "Featured" button. Below the navigation bar, the title "Mobility Aids for OT" is displayed, along with the author "By kotchet in Technology" and statistics: "Assistive-technology", "1,325", "9", "2", and "Featured". Below the text, there are two side-by-side photographs of a person demonstrating the use of a walker. The person is wearing a blue denim shirt, a black top, black pants, and brown boots. The background shows a hallway with a "FIRE EXIT" sign.

The screenshot shows the Instructables website interface for "Step 3: Walking With a Single Point Cane". The browser address bar shows the URL "https://www.instructables.com/id/Mobility-Aids-for-OT/". Below the navigation bar, the title "Step 3: Walking With a Single Point Cane" is displayed. Below the text, there are three side-by-side photographs of a person demonstrating the use of a single point cane. The person is wearing a blue denim shirt, a black top, black pants, and brown boots. The background shows a hallway with a "FIRE EXIT" sign.

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Mobility-Aids-for-OT/>

2.7.2

THERAPY

 instructables Let's Make ... Login | Sign Up

Classes Contests Community Teachers AUTODESK. Make anything

Stress-Reducing Weighted Blanket

By emilygrackin in Home > Health 37,664 604 125 Featured

cdn.instructables.com/FWL/BTA5/J8F5WT5G/FWL/BTA5/J8F5WT5G/LARGE.jpg

Step 1: Tools and Materials

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Stress-Reducing-Weighted-Blanket/>

2.7.3

THERAPY

Overview

- Things
- Story
 - Medicine Reminder
 - Project Goals
 - Design Considerations
 - Hexiwear Reminder Device
 - Hexiwear Raspberry Pi BLE, status 9/24/2016
 - Workaround being considered
 - Hexiwear Raspberry Pi BLE, status 10/02/2016
 - Arduinokit Einwin 360 Aacinn
 - Custom parts and enclosures
 - Schematics
 - Code
 - Credits

Tom Minnich
Published July 25, 2016 © GPL3+

Medicine Reminder Raspberry Pi, Alexa Voice and Hexiwear

Helpful reminders to take medicines on time, make medicines more effective, using Raspberry Pi, Alexa Voice and Hexiwear!

🔔 **Advanced** 📖 Full instructions provided ⌚ 20 hours 👁 1,438

Hey stranger! Sign up to access unlimited projects featuring Amazon Alexa and more – it's fr

The screenshot shows the AWS IoT console interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs for Resources, MQTT Client, Tunnel, Settings, and Notifications. Below this, there are several icons representing different IoT services. A central message states: "Your thing has been created. You can now connect a device to this thing, or add a rule that will trigger actions when your thing publishes a message." A blue button labeled "View thing" is prominent. Below the message, there is a search bar and a table of resources. The table has columns for Name, REST API endpoint, Thing type, MQTT topic, Last updated, Attributes used in a thing search, and Linked certificates. The first row is highlighted in red and contains the following data: Name: Tom_Mynich, REST API endpoint: https://mythings11704981.us-east-1.amazonaws.com/thingtypes/MyThing, Thing type: MyThingType, MQTT topic: /mythings11704981/us-east-1/MyThingType, Last updated: 7/25/2016, Attributes used in a thing search: None, and Linked certificates: None.

Sign up to access unlimited projects featuring Amazon Alexa and more – it's free.

2.7.4

THERAPY

<https://www.instructables.com/id/One-Leg-Therapy-Stool-Autism/>

2.7.5

THERAPY

The screenshot shows a product page on MyMiniFactory. The header includes the MyMiniFactory logo and navigation links: SCARICA, STORE NEW, CONCORSI, and HOW IT WORKS. On the right, there are buttons for SEARCH, SHARE, and REGISTRATI. The main image shows a person's hands holding a blue and orange 3D printed orthotic swimming fin. To the right of the image is a product information panel with the title "3D printed orthotic swimming fin", published 7 months ago. It lists the creator as BCN3D Technologies (@BCN3D) with 12 objects and 48 followers. There is a "TIP ME" button for \$2. Below this are options for "Free Download" or "Save for later". A "Click & Print preview" button is also present. The description section is partially visible, mentioning the fin's purpose for rehabilitation.

MyMiniFactory SCARICA STORE **NEW** CONCORSI HOW IT WORKS

SEARCH SHARE REGISTRATI EN

3D printed orthotic swimming fin

Published 7 months ago

 BCN3D Technologies
@BCN3D
12 objects
48 Followers

\$2 TIP ME

Free Download OR Save for later

Click & Print preview

Description

Two industrial designers from Barcelona have created a swimming fin to accelerate the rehabilitation of Pedro, a 16-year-old boy who suffered a stroke, which paralyzed half part of his body.

Pedro is a sixteen years old guy from Barcelona who loves sports.

<https://www.myminifactory.com/it/object/3d-print-3d-printed-orthotic-swimming-fin-67635>

2.7.6

OUR LEARNINGS

- The Therapy field of application is primarily aimed at people who have a therapeutic approach to people with disabilities - whether they are professionals or relatives. The background is that even for the therapy of niche challenges there are often no good commercial solutions because the circle of users is too small to establish profitable business models based on them.
- Similar to the field of "Learning Support", the project group assumes that two dimensions need to be highlighted here: on the one hand process knowledge about therapeutic measures, on the other hand concrete connected hardware solutions that can also be used in concrete terms.
- From our project perspective, it is crucial to get in touch with therapeutic experts and find out for which special purposes they have already developed solutions or for which they still lack solutions. In this sense, efforts in this field can be understood as "train-the-trainers" and "learn-from-the-trainers" categories.

2.8.1

CAREWARE

Adaptive Jacket Modification

By gluckc in Craft > Sewing 306 2

By **gluckc**
Follow

More by the author:

I am continuing my quest for clothes that are easy to put on and take off. Our son has muscular dystrophy and contractures in his elbows -- which keeps his arms at roughly 90 degrees. It makes putting on and taking off jackets difficult. So, my idea was to essentially make the arm hole a whole lot bigger.

Step 4: Stitch a Second Time Around

This step isn't necessary. I turned the jacket rightside out and sewed a second stitch around the entire cutout.

Add Tip Ask Question Comment Download

Step 5: Repeat for the Other Arm and DONE

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Adaptive-Jacket-Modification/>

2.8.2

CAREWARE

Ahmed Elagaan
Published November 20, 2016

Color Detector for Blind People

When you put anything in front of your mobile camera and push the button, your mobile will say the color of that thing.

👉 Easy 📄 Full instructions provided ⌚ 8 hours 👁️ 2,059

Step 3: Download the 1Shield Application

For Android smartphones, download the application [here](#). For iOS smartphones download the application from [here](#).

https://www.hackster.io/ahmed_elsagaan/color-detector-for-blind-people-87161d

2.8.3

CAREWARE

MyMiniFactory

SCARICA

STORE **NEW**

CONCORSI

HOW IT WORKS

🔍

SHARE

🇮🇹

🛒

REGISTR

3D

Shoelace tie helper

Published 2 years ago

Edison Siu
@EdisonSiu

2 objects

1 Follower

\$2 - TIP ME

Free Download

OR

Save for later

Click & Print preview

Description

Most common everyday practical shoes have laces on them. However, tying them is a nearly impossible task for someone with limited mobility in their hands. This device simplifies the process of tying shoes by incorporating a screwing method. The device allows you to insert your shoelaces in and screw in the bolt to tie your shoes by inserting the lace into the hole of the large ring attached to the bolt sleeve, and then loop it over and placing the aglet (plastic tip commonly found on the end of shoelaces) onto the top of the bolt into the

SHOW MORE

Technical Information

Object Parts

Tags

##enabledby3d

Ad closed by Google

Stop seeing this ad Why this ad?

<https://www.myminifactory.com/it/object/3d-print-shoelace-tie-helper-24406>

2.8.4

OUR LEARNINGS

- It is remarkable how little the common online repositories for Open Health solutions address clothing issues. For many people with physical disabilities, commercial clothing does not work. In addition, smart textiles offer particularly great potential for users with disabilities: for example, they make it possible to dispense with costly external aids by simply integrating them into clothing.
- However, it is also understandable that so few "Careware" projects can be found on the established online repositories: the production of textiles requires suitable workshops and not many Fab Labs have enough textile machines.

2.9.1

FUN & LEISURE TIME

 instructables Let's Make ...

[Classes](#) [Contests](#) [Community](#) [Teachers](#)

Water Scooter for Disabled Child

By shawminello in Technology > Assistive-technology 👁️ 14,202 ❤️ 70 💬 40 ★ Featured

<https://cdn.instructables.com/FT6KPNZ/GGC2TWPV/FT6KPNZGGC2TWPV.LARGE.jpg>

Step 1: Collect What You Will Need.

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Water-Scooter-for-Disabled-Child/>

2.9.2

FUN & LEISURE TIME

 instructables Let's Make ... [Featured](#) [Write an instructable](#)

[Classes](#) [Contests](#) [Community](#) [Teachers](#)

Wiimote Modification for Persons With Disabilities

By CATEA in Technology - Assistive-technology [👁 8,129](#) [❤ 17](#) [👍 11](#) [★ Featured](#)

cdn.instructables.com/FDXYM8T/GE3BR6KO/FDXYM8TGE3BR6KO.LARGE.jpg

Step 9: Assemble the Wiimote

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Wiimote-Modification-for-Persons-with-Disabilities-1/>

2.9.3

FUN & LEISURE TIME

HACKADAY.IO Projects Lists Contests Stack More Search projects, profiles... Sign up Log In

ScottCar A Go-Kart for a special child

A go-kart with an electrical emergency braking system for our disabled son

Alain Mauer

Follow project Like project Join this project

3.6k views 10 comments 61 followers 33 likes

Description Details Files Components Logs Instructions Discussion

DESCRIPTION

I build this car for our autistic son. Scott has 11 years now and he loves bobby-cars, but he is too tall now. A go-kart is not an option, because he does not know how to handle pedals and brakes.

Windows taskbar: ScottCar A Go-Kart fo... 61% 13:22

2017 cottCar

a go-kart for a child with special needs

View Gallery

Windows taskbar: ScottCar A Go-Kart fo...

<https://hackaday.io/project/21018-scottcar-a-go-kart-for-a-special-child>

2.9.4

FUN & LEISURE TIME

<https://www.instructables.com/id/Head-Mouse-Game-controller-or-disability-aid/>

2.9.5

OUR LEARNINGS

- Another category that is strongly underestimated is "Fun & Leisure Time". By this we mean all solutions that playfully improve the quality of life of people with disabilities. Many conventional games - digital or analogue - cannot simply be used by people with disabilities. The controllers of game consoles are just as standardized as forks or spoons. The project group has a huge potential in this field of application, because good solutions in this field can trigger particular enthusiasm and commitment, as our qualitative interviews have shown.

3 - Next steps: how to move forward
and to improve version 1 of our Open
Healthcare Map?

3.1

NEXT STEPS

The Open Healthcare Map presented here is only a first version. The project group sees it as a work in progress that should be maintained and expanded as the project progresses and beyond. It is to serve also in the future as first orientation for people who are interested in Open Health & Wellbeing. In the further course of our project we will improve and extend the Open Healthcare Map as follows:

1. Both the nine **fields of application and the selected best practices so far have to be sharpened or extended if necessary**; this also applies to the overlaps indicated above.
2. The **analysis** of best practices, which was decisive for our selection but was not extended, should be published in a shortened, manageable form.
3. The best practices should be presented in a way that is already **synchronized with the architecture and user interface of the careables.org platform**.

3.2

WORK WITH US!

Careables is a distinctly open project that invites collaborators of all kinds to promote the worldwide availability of Open Health & Wellbeing solutions. For this reason, **we would like to invite the reader to get in touch with us to make improvements.** We are particularly interested in the input of groups of actors who have specific expertise in health & wellbeing areas, on the basis of which further use cases can be developed.

We are looking forward to your message to info@careables.org!

3.3

References

- Homan C.M., Schull J.I., Prabhu, A., (2017) On the Genesis of an Assistive Technology Crowdsourcing Community. Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems <https://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=3053356>
- Buehler et al. (2015) Sharing is Caring: Assistive Technology Designs on Thingiverse, CHI 2015, Crossings, Seoul, Korea
<https://parasol.tamu.edu/craw/dreu2016/Hofmann/uploads/5/6/7/3/56734939/p525-buehler.pdf>
- Amy Hurst: Challenges and Opportunities for Integrating 3D Printing into Physical Therapy
<https://archive.hshsl.umaryland.edu/bitstream/10713/7602/1/Hurst%20-%20Challenges%20and%20Opportunities.pdf>

Deliverable 2.1

Open Healthcare Map v1

A selection of 45 best practices in 9 fields of application in Open Healthcare,
sourced from online repositories.

Date

December 2018

Dissemination Level

Public

Responsible Partners

Makea

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